

Kaloplocamus ramosus (Cantraine, 1835) (Gastropoda: Polyceridae): new records in the Bay of Biscay, with notes on distribution and food

Kaloplocamus ramosus (Cantraine, 1835) (Gastropoda: Polyceridae): nuevos sitios en el Golfo de Vizcaya, con datos sobre su distribución y su dieta

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ABSTRACT

Many specimens of *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835) were collected in the Bay of Biscay during Ifremer's EVHOE scientific cruises in 2009 and 2010 (October – November). This species is new to the French Atlantic coast, which is its most northern known occurrence, and a map of its distribution in the Bay of Biscay is provided. Two prey-species (Bryozoa) were observed from gut contents. One of these, *Cellaria salicornioides*, is an addition to the known food-list of *K. ramosus*. Data on the taxonomy are given and *Doris fimbriata* delle Chiaje, 1841 is added to the synonymy of *K. ramosus*.

RÉSUMÉ

De nombreux spécimens de *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835) ont été récoltés dans le golfe de Gascogne au cours des campagnes scientifiques Ifremer EVHOE de 2009 et 2010 (octobre – novembre). L'espèce est nouvelle pour les côtes atlantiques françaises qui représentent sa latitude la plus nordique, et une carte de sa distribution dans le Golfe de Gascogne est présentée. Deux espèces de Bryozoa ont été trouvées dans le contenu stomacal. L'une d'entre elles, *Cellaria salicornioides*, est mentionnée pour la première fois comme nourriture pour *K. ramosus*. Des informations sur la taxonomie sont fournies et *Doris fimbriata* delle Chiaje, 1841 est ajoutée à la synonymie de *K. ramosus*.

RESUMEN

Numerosos ejemplares de *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835) fueron recogidos en el Golfo de Vizcaya durante las campañas científicas Ifremer EVHOE en 2009 y 2010 (entre octubre y noviembre). La especie es nueva para la costa Atlántica francesa, lo cual representa la cita más septentrional conocida, y se presenta un mapa de su distribución en el Golfo de Vizcaya. Dos especies-presa (Bryozoa) fueron observadas en el contenido estomacal. Una de ellas, *Cellaria salicornioides*, se añade a la lista de presas conocidas de esta especie. Se incluye un mapa de distribución en el Golfo de Vizcaya así como también datos sobre la taxonomía, añadiendo *Doris fimbriata* Delle Chiaje, 1841 a la sinonimia de *K. ramosus*.

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Figure 1. Map 1. EVHOE 2009-2010. Sampling area and stations. Some symbols of stations (O1016/N0817, O0991/N0779, O0992/N0780) overlap, see Table I. Stars represent localities where *Kaloplocamus ramosus* was found.

Figura 1. Mapa 1. EVHOE 2009-2010. Área y estaciones de muestreo. Algunos símbolos de estaciones (O1016/N0817, O0991/N0779, O0992/N0780) se confunden, véase la Tabla I. Las estrellas representan localidades en las que se encontró *Kaloplocamus ramosus*.

INTRODUCTION

Opisthobranchs are well recorded in the southern part of the Bay of Biscay (GARCÍA AND BERTSCH 2009) as well as in the Celtic Sea and the English Channel (HAYWARD AND RYLAND 1990). However, they have been less well investigated in the northern part of the Bay of Biscay, which is the northern limit of the Lusitanian Province. During recent EVHOE (Evaluation Halieutique pour l'Ouest de l'Europe) scientific cruises in this area, whose main purpose was to assess the

state of the stock of commercially valuable species (fishes, cephalopods, crustacea), numerous specimens of the opisthobranch *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835) were collected for the first time.

K. ramosus is a widespread species, living mainly in temperate waters, but also reported in tropical waters (e.g. East coast of South Africa (BERGH 1907) and the Hawaiian Islands (PITTMAN AND FIENE 2010)).

The present paper reports on geographic distribution, taxonomy, anatomy, food and habitat of *K. ramosus*.

Table I. *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835). Sample data. All specimens collected by Jocelyne Martin and Pascal Laffargue/Ifremer, determined by Alex Vanhaelen/RBINS. Cruise ref. nbr: cruise reference number; Station ref. nbr: station reference number; Station references: N= 2009, O= 2010; qty= quantity. Total stations: 18. Total specimens: 89 (87 at RBINS, 2 at Ifremer).

Tabla I. *Kaloplocamus ramosus* (Cantraine, 1835). Datos de nuestro. Todos los ejemplares recolectados por Jocelyne Martin y Pascal Laffargue/Ifremer, identificados por Alex Vanhaelen/RBINS. Cruise ref. nbr: número de referencia de la campaña; Station ref. nbr: número de referencia de la estación; Datos de la estación: N= 2009, O= 2010; qty= cantidad. Total de estaciones: 18. Especímenes totales: 89 (87 de RBINS, 2 de Ifremer).

RBINS INV.nbr	Cruise ref. nbr	Station ref. nbr	specim, qty	Geographic latitude	coordinates longitude	Collection dates	Depth (m)
98002	EVHOE2009	N0779	1	N 45° 38' 20.1"	W 3° 13' 28.7"	21-10-2009	137
98003	EVHOE2009	N0780	1	N 45° 45' 25.2"	W 3° 23' 13.8"	21-10-2009	150
98004\]	EVHOE2009	N0796	8	N 46° 28' 09.7"	W 3° 51' 23.4"	25-10-2009	142
98019	EVHOE2009	N0797	12	N 46° 12' 23.0"	W 4° 08' 34.7"	26-10-2009	180
98007\]	EVHOE2009	N0799	8	N 46° 36' 05.1"	W 4° 13' 43.9"	26-10-2009	150
98009	EVHOE2009	N0802	5	N 46° 45' 37.3"	W 4° 28' 47.5"	27-10-2009	148
98010	EVHOE2009	N0817	1	N 47° 10' 27.3"	W 4° 48' 28.2"	04-11-2009	134
Ifremer	EVHOE2009	N0817	1	N 47° 10' 27.3"	W 4° 48' 28.2"	04-11-2009	134
98011	EVHOE2009	N0820	1	N 46° 51' 35.1"	W 5° 11' 27.7"	05-11-2009	185
98012	EVHOE2009	N0822	1	N 47° 4' 58.1"	W 5° 10' 56.2"	05-11-2009	159
98021	EVHOE2010	O0954	15	N 45° 30' 12.9"	W 3° 5' 49.3"	21-10-2010	147
98022	EVHOE2010	O0961	2	N 45° 12' 39.5"	W 2° 32' 29.2"	22-10-2010	130
Ifremer	EVHOE2010	O0962	1	N 45° 16' 24.0"	W 2° 46' 18.1"	22-10-2010	133
98023	EVHOE2010	O0991	19	N 45° 37' 27.3"	W 3° 13' 34.9"	29-10-2010	137
98024	EVHOE2010	O0992	8	N 45° 45' 21.6"	W 3° 23' 13.7"	29-10-2010	149
98025	EVHOE2010	O1011	1	N 46° 54' 14.2"	W 4° 36' 17.4"	04-11-2010	144
98026	EVHOE2010	O1016	2	N 47° 10' 30.2"	W 4° 48' 25.8"	05-11-2010	131
98027	EVHOE2010	O1025	1	N 47° 22' 3.1"	W 4° 55' 30.3"	07-11-2010	128
98028	EVHOE2010	O1026	1	N 47° 23' 51.5"	W 5° 14' 28.2"	07-11-2010	139

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The specimens were collected at 18 stations off southern Brittany (Fig. 1, Table I) during the EVHOE surveys on board R/V *Thalassa*. During October and November of 2009 and 2010, 142 bottom trawls (stations) were performed each year.

The sampling method includes diurnal standardized 30 minutes bottom trawls at a speed of 4 knots, using a GOV-36/47 otter trawl, 20 m wide, 4 m high with a 20 mm mesh codend. This gear is not adapted to capture small benthic species (<3-4 cm) such as *K. ramosus*. Therefore the absence of this species at some stations could be an artefact. For

the same reason, the population density could be underestimated.

Geographical coordinates, depths, sea water temperatures and nature of the bottom were recorded during the hauls. All data pertaining to a given station were uploaded in a database at Ifremer.

Contents of the trawl's pocket were sorted on board. Unidentified opisthobranchia were sorted, photographed when in good condition and properly labeled prior to fixation, usually in a 70% ethanol solution or deep-frozen. Specimens were sent to RBINS for identification and transferred to a 70% ethanol, borax-buffered, (pH 8.0) solution.

The radula of specimen N0799/07 was dissected, critical point dried and

gold-coated to perform SEM photographs with RBIN's FEI-QUANTA-200 ESEM (Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope) (Fig. 7).

Ten specimens (one per station, except for station O-1016) were dissected for identification of gut contents. Those stations were selected along a line joining the most southeasterly station (O-0961) to the most northwesterly station (O-1026), at the most regular possible intervals. Stations concerned were N-0796, N-0817, N-0822, O-0954, O-0961, O-0922, O-1016 (2 specimens), O-1025 and O-1026. Gut content was immersed during 10 minutes in commercial bleach, and then rinsed several times in tap water. The bryozoa were identified according to DE BLAUWE (2009).

RESULTS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1797
Family POLYCERIDAE Alder & Hancock, 1845
Genus *Kaloplocamus* Bergh, 1880 [1879]
Kaloplocamus ramosus (Cantraine, 1835)

- Doris ramosa* Cantraine, 1835: Bull. Acad. R. Belg., 2: 383; 1841, *Nouv. Mém. Acad. R. Sci. Bruxelles*, 13: 54, pl. 3 fig. 7. [type locality: Split (as Spalato), Croatia, type specimen lost].
- Euplocamus croceus* Philippi, 1836, *Enum. Moll. Sicil.*, 1: 103, pl. 7 fig. 1 [Palermo (as Panormi), Italy]. —Bergh, 1880, *Verh. zool.-bot. Ges. Wien*, 29: 625
- Euplocamus frondosus* Philippi, 1839, *Arch. Naturgesch.*, 5 (1): 114, pl. 3 fig. 1 [Sicily, Italy].
- Doris fimbriata* delle Chiaje, 1841, *Descr. Anim. s. Vert.*, 2: 21; 5: 77; 6: pl. 44, Figs 7-10. [Napoli, Italy] — *new synonym*.
- Triopa yatesi* Angas, 1864, *J. Conchyl., Paris*, 12: 60, col. pl. v, Fig. 8. [Watson Bay, S.E. Australia].
- Euplocamus ramosus* —Bergh, 1880, *Verh. zool.-bot. Ges. Wien*, 29: 625, in synonymy of *Euplocamus croceus* Phil., erroneously credited to "Phil. Malacol. médit. 1840. p. 54. pl. 3. Fig. 7.". This is clearly confusion with Cantraine's 1841 publication, cited with a wrong date.
- Euplocamus capensis*; Bartsch, 1915, *Bull. U.S. natn. Mus.* 91: 239, 212.
- Kaloplocamus aureus* Odhner, 1932, *Ark. Zool.*, 23. A. (14): 41, fig. 11-12. [Bahía del Confital (juv.) Gran Canaria].
- Kaloplocamus ramosus* —Pruvot-Fol, 1951, *Arch. Zool. exp. gén.*, 88 (1): 35, pl. 2 Figs 3, 16. [juvenile from Banyuls, France] (generic name misspelled).
- Euplocamus plumosus* Schultz —Pruvot-Fol, 1954, *Faune Fr.*, 58: 323. (not *Euplocamus plumosus* W. Thompson, 1840, a junior synonym of *Limacia clavigera* (O. F. Müller, 1776)). [Sicily, Italy] (this name could not be traced elsewhere).
- Kaloplocamus filusius* Cattaneo-Vietti and Sordi, 1988, *Basteria*, 52: 50, fig. 1-12. [Tuscany, Italy].

Thirty nine specimens of *K. ramosus* were collected during the 2009 cruise and fifty during the 2010 cruise.

Anatomy: The body of live specimens (Fig. 2) is slug-like and about 3 times longer than broad. Extended lengths are

Except for two specimens kept at Ifremer/Nantes (Ref. EVHOE2009-N0817/02 and EVHOE2010-O962), the collection was deposited at RBINS (general catalogue number IG-31.621) and assigned an individual Recent Invertebrates Department code number in the series INV.98.001 to INV.98.028

Two specimens from sample N0817 were photographed in a sea water filled container, alive, relaxed and extended, prior to fixation in ethanol (Fig. 2).

Photographs of preserved material were taken through the ocular of a dissecting microscope with a handheld camera.

For nomenclature we chose to follow the CLEMAM taxonomic database.

between 29 and 33 mm. Contracted bodies measure from 16 to 28 mm long. The buccal mass is more or less evaginated in most specimens. Transversal section at mid-body is quadrangular. The sole is smooth. Anterior edge of

Figures 2-5. *Kaloplocamus ramosus*. 2: dorsal view of two living specimens relaxed in sea water (sample N0817); 3: branched processes on oral veil (arrows); 4: oral tentacle (arrow); 5: eyes on dorsum of specimen N0822 (arrows). Figure 6. Bryozoa extracted from gut of specimen N0796/08. A: *Cellaria salicornioides*; B: *Caberea boryi*.

Figuras 2-5. Kaloplocamus ramosus. 2: vista dorsal de dos ejemplares vivos relajados en agua de mar (muestra N0817); 3: papillas ramosas del velo oral (flechas); 4: tentáculo oral (flecha); 5: ojos en el dorso del espécimen N0822 (flechas). Figura 6. Briozoos extraídos del estómago del espécimen N0796/08. A: *Cellaria salicornioides*, B: *Caberea boryi*.

propodium is horizontally bilamellated. No propodial tentacles are noticed. Lateral edges are thick, narrow and undulating.

In front, the oral veil is slightly rounded, with 6-7 velar processes, here-

after named 'branched processes', bearing short secondary papillae on their distal third. (Fig. 3).

The dorsum is lined by a longitudinal row of 5 similar but larger branching processes, the first in the row starting

Table II. *Kaloplocamus ramosus*. Known prey-species.
 Tabla II. *Kaloplocamus ramosus*. *Especies de presas conocidas*.

Name in literature	Valid name according to WoRMS	Reference
<i>Acamarchis</i> cf. <i>dentata</i>	<i>Bugula neritina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	CANTRAINE (1841: 55)
<i>Bugula</i> sp.	<i>Bugula</i> Oken, 1815	VAYSSIÈRE (1901: 68)
<i>Caberea boryi</i>	<i>Caberea boryi</i> (Audouin, 1826)	BERGH (1880: 634) [1879], this paper
<i>Caberea</i> sp.	<i>Caberea</i> Lamouroux, 1816	PERRONE (1985: 102)
<i>Cellaria salicornioides</i>	<i>Cellaria salicornioides</i> Lamouroux, 1816	this paper
<i>Cellularia scabra</i>	? <i>Scrupocellaria scabra</i> (Van Beneden, 1848)	BERGH (1880: 634) [1879]
<i>Porella cervicornis</i>	<i>Smittina (Porella) cervicornis</i> (Pallas, 1766)	PERRONE (1985: 102)
<i>Retepora</i> sp.	<i>Reteporella grimaldii</i> (Jullien, 1903)	VAYSSIÈRE (1901: 68)
<i>Scrupocellaria</i> cf. <i>reptans</i>	<i>Scrupocellaria</i> cf. <i>reptans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	CATTANEO-VIETTI AND SORDI (1988: 51)
<i>Scrupocellaria incurvata</i>	<i>Scrupocellaria incurvata</i> Waters, 1897	CATTANEO-VIETTI AND SORDI (1988: 51)
<i>Tubocellaria</i> (*) <i>cereoides</i> (sic)	<i>Margaretta cereoides</i> (Ellis & Solander, 1786)	PERRONE (1985: 102)

(*) error for *Tubocellaria* d'Orbigny, 1852

just behind and under the level of the rhinophores, the others on the dorsum.

A typical doridian branchial plume is present on the dorsal median, at two thirds of posterior body length.

Basic colour of head, dorsum, metapodium, stalk of rhinophores, stalk of velar and dorsal processes is creamy-yellow. Surface of dorsum and flanks can be speckled (not in all specimens) with small, randomly dispersed, whitish warts (or minute tubercles) of variable size and number.

Clavus of rhinophores is greenish-yellow, somewhat darker on one of the specimens. Branchial plume has a somewhat darker yellow tinge than the body base colour. Colour of all specimens is uniform light beige, with no pigment observed. Head, dorsum, metapodium, velar and dorsal processes are speckled with dark-reddish to brown spots in variable densities and blots.

Oral tentacle on each side of head, under oral veil, is flat, rectangular, with the two short sides somewhat rounded, and is afixed to the body wall by one of its longer sides. Ratio length to width = 2.5 to 3. (Fig. 4).

Rhinophore stalks are generally retracted in mantle pocket; clavus (lamelated cone) is protruding 50 to 100% from the dorsum and bears between 14 and 31 thin complete or partial lamellae.

The observed number of lamellae is dependent on the integrity (intact, flattened) and degree of contraction and retraction of the clavus.

One sample (N0796/07) shows a circle-shaped ripple around the rhinophore's base.

On the dorsum sides, a faint pallial ridge can sometimes be seen, starting behind the rhinophores and fading away besides the branchial plume. The first pair of the 5 dorsal branched processes is located just under and slightly behind the rhinophore basis; pairs 2 and 3 (generally the largest) stand on the pallial ridge, between the rhinophores and branchial plume; pair 4 is near the plume and pair 5 is at the rear, between the plume and metapodium.

The non-retracted branchial plume is composed of 5 tripinnate gills arranged in a horseshoe around the anal papilla.

A large genital pore is located on the right side, under and between the first and second dorsal branched processes.

Three specimens (N0796/02, N0796/03 and N0822) show a pair of tiny symmetrical dark spots embedded in the dorsal epidermis behind the rhinophores (Fig. 5).

The apparent absence of some characters (*i.e.* the absence of the minute rhinophoral sheath) can be an artefact resulting from the preserving technique.

Figure 7. *Kaloplocamus ramosus*. Radula of specimen N0799/7. A: full view; B: hooked 3rd lateral tooth (arrow) and dish-like rectangular 4th to n-th lateral teeth (arrows a, b, c). SEM photos by J. Cellis and L. Despontin.

Figura 7. *Kaloplocamus ramosus*. Rádula del espécimen N0799/7. A: vista completa; B: tercer diente lateral ganchudo (flecha) y dientes rectangulares y aplanados desde los cuartos; C: los tres primeros dientes laterales ganchudos (flechas a, b, c). Fotos al MEB por J. Cellis y L. Despontin.

The radula (Fig. 7) presents 17 rows of denticles. In a typical row, from axis to the outer side, the center (rachis) is free of denticles; the first to 3rd lateral denticles are long, narrow hooks; the 4th to the 15,16 or 17th laterals are shallow rectangular dish-like platelets, giving the radular formula $17 \times [(15-17).3.0.3. (17-15)]$.

Diet: Large pieces (from 1.5 to 2.2 mm long) of Bryozoa were found in the anterior part of the digestive tract of most dissected specimens (Table II).

Some specimens showed only one prey-species: *Cellaria salicornioides* Lamouroux, 1816 (in N0822, O0954, O0961 and O0922) or *Caberea boryi* (Audouin, 1826) (in O1026) (Fig. 6). One specimen (N0796) contained the two above-mentioned prey-species. The digestive tract was found empty in four of the dissected specimens.

DISCUSSION

Taxonomy

According to literature, *K. ramosus* has been allocated to 6 different genera (*Caloplocamus*, *Doris*, *Euplocamus*, *Idalia*, *Kaloplocamus* and *Triopa*) and cited under 14 different species names (*aureus*, *capensis*, *croceus*, *croceus* var. *capensis*, *filosus*, *fimbriata*, *frondosus*, *japonicus*, *longicornis*, *orientalis*, *plumosus*, *principiswalliae*, *tristis* and *yatesi*), indicating a highly variable species with a very large distribution area.

For an extensive review of its taxonomy, we refer to VALLÈS AND GOSLINER (2006) and EDMUNDS (2010).

Anatomy

General shape, body size, colour, dorsal appendages, smooth sole, number of rhinophore lamellae, 15 to 18 branched processes, oral tentacles and radula of observed specimens fit well with *K. ramosus* (see CANTRAINE 1835, 1841; PHILIPPI 1836, 1844; DELLE CHIAJE 1841; BERGH 1880 [1879], 1883, 1892, 1899; VAYSSIÈRE 1901, 1913; PRUVOT-FOL 1951, 1954; MACNAE 1958; SCHMEKEL AND PORTMANN 1982; CATTANEO-VIETTI AND SORDI 1988; BABA 1989; ORTEA-RATO, MORO-ABAD AND CA-

Distribution and ecology: Sampling stations of the Bay of Biscay where *K. ramosus* specimens were collected cover an area of about 350 km long and 70 km wide, oriented along a SE-NW axis, some 120 km southwards off Brittany's south western coast, between 45° 12' 39.5" N – 02° 32' 29.2" W and 47° 23' 51.5" N – 05° 14' 28.2" W (Fig. 1 and Table I).

Collected specimens were trawled on the Bay of Biscay and Celtic Sea continental shelves from depths ranging from 128 m (station O1025) to 185 m (station N0820) on soft bottoms (ranging from sand to muddy sand) (Fig. 1). Bottom temperatures during collection ranged from 11.19 to 11.85° C. Whatever the season, mean bottom temperatures in that area are rather stable, ranging from 10.8 to 11.9° C.

BALLER-GUTIÉRREZ 2001 and VALLÈS AND GOSLINER 2006).

The number of pallial and velar processes might be size-dependent: VAYSSIÈRE (1901) mentions 3-4 processes per side for "juveniles", 5 processes for 25-38 mm long specimens and 6 for the "largest".

Taxonomic confusion of *K. ramosus* is certainly related, at least partly, to the large variability of its colour patterns, going from creamy to brick red. However, there is apparently no relationship between colour patterns and distribution. The colour range of *K. ramosus* varies widely from translucent white with yellow-orange spots (RUDMAN, 2010a in Hong Kong) to pale grey with light orange-red spots (EDMUNDS 2010: Fig. 1-F, in Ghana) to pale yellow cream with orange variously dispersed speckles (Baba 1949: pl. XIII, Figs 46-47, in Japan) or with dark-brown speckles (our specimens in Atlantic France, Fig. 2) to almost uniform bright red with minute light yellow-orange spots (WIRTZ AND DEBELIUS 2003: 214, in the Azores). No particular colour pattern seems to be locality-

dependent and different patterns are sometimes observed simultaneously at the same location.

Other *Kaloplocamus* species (e.g. *K. acutus*) also present a large colour variability with stable external morphological characters such as the branching processes (BABA 1955; BOLLAND 2006a, b and RUDMAN 2010a, b).

The two tiny dark spots embedded in the epidermis of the dorsum, behind the rhinophores, are probably rudimentary eyes. They have been mentioned by DELLE CHIAJE (1841 (2): 29) (as *Doris fimbriata*), BERGH (1883: 142) and VAYSSIÈRE (1901: 69, pl. V, Fig. 2) and drawn by BABA (1949 pl. XIII Figs 46, 47). Several photographs of live specimens (not collected) showing the eyes can be viewed on Pitmann and Fienne's, and on Johnson's websites.

Diet

The diet of *K. ramosus* is usually broadly referred to as "bryozoans". Eight bryozoans have been identified by different authors to species level (Table II), all from the Mediterranean Sea. *Caberea boryi* (Audouin, 1826) is also found in our specimen (N0796/08). *Cellaria salicornioides* Lamouroux, 1816 is a new known prey in the diet of *K. ramosus*. Our observations and data from literature listed in Table II confirm that *K. ramosus* feeds mostly on branching Bryozoans.

The restricted number of prey-species known so far is almost certainly an artefact, being only reported from the Mediterranean Sea and the Bay of Biscay.

Distribution

K. ramosus is recorded for the first time in the Bay of Biscay. The large area where specimens were collected during the EVOHE 2009 and 2010 cruises and their large number (89) indicates that we are dealing with a well established population. The Bay of Biscay extends the distribution of *K. ramosus*, a temperate, sometimes tropical, species to its most northerly known latitude, at the northern limit of the Lusitanian Province.

According to literature and websites, the species is nearly cosmopolitan but not yet mentioned from the Americas and the Philippines.

The present worldwide distribution of *K. ramosus* and its potential taxonomic confusion (14 synonyms recognized) leads us to suspect that we are dealing either with a highly variable species or with a species complex. As already suggested by VALLÈS AND GOSLINER (2006), Rudman (several SEASLUGFORUM messages) and EDMUNDS (2010), these hypotheses should be tested via DNA analysis of material proceeding from the different areas.

Ecology

Collecting depths (128-185 m) of our material are in agreement with those reported in the literature (5-400 m) (WIRTZ 1998: 12; EDMUNDS 2010: 296; KOUTSOUBAS, TSELEPIDES AND ELEFTHERIOU 2000: 91; ZSILAVECZ 2007).

Kaloplocamus ramosus is known from soft bottoms (PRUVOT-FOL 1951; WIRZ-MANGOLD AND WYSS 1958; RÓS 1975; KOUTSOUBAS ET AL. 2000; DOMÈNECH, AVILA AND BALLESTEROS 2006; present study) and hard bottoms (AVÍLA, AZEVEDO, GONÇALVES, FONTES AND CARDIGOS 1998; GARCÍA-GÓMEZ 2002; CERVERA, CALADO, GAVAIÁ, MALAQUIAS, TEMPLADO, BALLESTEROS, GARCÍA-GÓMEZ AND MEGINA 2004; MALAQUIAS, CALADO, PADULA AND CERVERA 2009; RUDMAN 2010a; BOLLAND 2006; PITTMAN AND FIENE 2010; SURG 2007; WIRTZ AND DEBELIUS 2003). This difference is mainly related to the collecting methods. Specimens collected by divers have been found on rocky bottom or wrecks, or in caves whereas dredging and bottom trawling is performed on soft bottom. The species is reported from moderately to highly exposed rocky habitats (PITTMAN AND FIENE 2010) as well as from moderate current areas (our study). *K. ramosus* is active day and night, under ledges or stones (JOHNSON 2005, WIRTZ AND DEBELIUS, 2003, PITTMAN AND FIENE 2010, MISENDEN 2005).

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